

Codes	More concise rewording (while keeping the spirit of the code)	Definition
challenges of becoming visible and reaching customers	Visibility and customer reach challenges	Business wants potential customers to be aware of product offering -- marketing strategies and ways of reaching customers
Compromises are challenging to discuss (shame)	Compromises are challenging to discuss (shame)	having experienced harms or attacks or losing money or any form of harm is hard for businesses to talk about. Any discussions where the participants indicates shame because of having been attacked
Credibility and trust (importance of appearances for customers) -- business credibility -- (Lack of credibility even if they have a clean history)	Credibility and trust	Descriptions of how sellers view that the credibility and trust of them and their business is weighed by other stakeholders (e.g., buyers and platforms). This also includes any descriptions of how sellers may attempt to improve their credibility and trust with buyers and platforms.
customers interfering with operations due to business message, identity, or ideology -- Product expresses buyer's moral values	Values-based customer interference	customer's identity or values influence product selection or misuse of customer-facing tools
expectation of operation in line with large businesses (buyer perspective)	Pressure to meet large-business standards	When buyers expect the seller to operate their business in the same way as a large business (e.g, a large online seller)
Fear of harm's impact influenced mitigation/protective behavior -- anxiety or self-questioning due to the experience of harms or hearing stories of other's experiences	Fear shapes protective behavior	Descriptions of fear or negative personal reactions to facing harm or hearing about harm faced by others.
Features of platforms	Features of platforms	Top level code describing platform features that sellers may use or may be used to harm sellers
folk theories about how systems work (percieved platform policies or functioning)	System folk theories	Platform policies and functions are interpreted by the seller, possibly correct or incorrect
giving up because they felt they couldn't solve the issue -- Distancing oneself from harm -- in-person seeming more safe given how bad online is!	Giving up on solutions	Harms and problems that cause sellers to disengage from the business, customer base, or platform
hypervigilance	hypervigilance	Scenarios where a seller describes increased awareness and proactive behaviors to avoid a particular form of harm or attack
hypervisibility	hypervisibility	Business or product gains unwanted notoriety
Identity and business mixed (ideology, politics, identity)	Identity-business entanglement	Product offering or business strategies strongly reflects personal identity/values.
Lack of control and meaningful decision making power	Lack of control	Platform policies compel sellers to operate in a specific way
Lack of legal support	No legal support	legal support is not available -- either very expensive or there is no legal method or law to be able to go after attackers
Lack of platform intervention -- Lack of Notification of Harms Taking Place	No platform intervention	Monitoring of harms is ineffective, incomplete, or not timely.
mental health effects of business related issues	Business harms mental health	effects of online interactions and attacks on the business on the owner/participant's mental health
Mention of attack experienced	Mention of attack experienced	Top level code describing an attack experienced by the seller

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minimal faith in platform support -- Expectations of platform to protect owner -- shared responsibility model to protect the business, assignment of protection responsibility is often unclear -- Feeling like platforms are not hearing their concerns (lack of support)	Minimal faith in platform	Platforms and sellers share responsibility for security. Some aspects handled by payment or seller platform, others by the seller. Often unclear where these boundaries lie.
Overhead for Resolving Harm (business disruption) -- time or financial -- recognition of harm takes time	Harm resolution overhead	Any sort of overhead, in terms of time or finances, that sellers face from a harm. This may include time to resolve business disruptions, financial losses, etc. . .
Owner puts trust in people (employee/friend) to handle business operation -- In-person relationships leading to online harms -- trust due to relational familiarity leading to harm (insider harm) -- Adversary placed in high-trust role -- Hiring adversary came from opportunity	Insider trust leading harm	Business personnel decisions strongly influenced by personal relationships
platform norm's influence on customer behavior	platform norm's influence on customer behavior	Platform norms or culture affects how customers interact with the seller
platform's lack of recognition of insider attacks	Insider attacks not recognized	When a platform does not recognize/does not acknowledge/does not offer resolution for an insider attack
Platforms have usability issues -- platforms are confusing and hard to work with (Platform requires technical expertise for using features)	Platform usability issues	Any description of platform features that are hard for the seller to use or are confusing/difficult to navigate/do not work as the seller expects.
Platforms make incident response difficult	Difficult incident response	Scenarios where a platform makes it difficult for sellers to navigate and respond to the compromise of seller's accounts
platforms making harms invisible	Platforms hide harms	platforms making it so people (other sellers, or buyers) can't tell that a shop was attacked and was harmed
platforms taking advantage of lack of competition (Platform fees are high/little competition for certain platforms/why is there only one YouTube?) -- Platforms are exploitative	Exploitative platforms	Sellers feel compelled to use certain platforms (Etsy or eBay or Spotify for example) due to lack of compelling alternatives
power dynamics that sellers are unfamiliar with -- customer having disproportionate ability to impact the seller -- Customer weaponizing platform policy to make threats NOTE: How does being a small business affect how certain things impact the business?	Customer policy weaponization	Tools available to customer can be used to harm the business
Protection and coping mechanisms	Protection and coping mechanisms	Top level code describing any personal or business protection/coping mechanisms the seller employs when faced with harm or well after facing the harm online (any action taken on the platforms or generally online)
Punishment instead of reward -- Platform objectives diverge from seller objectives	Punishment over reward	platforms have objectives (e.g., growth or only customer satisfaction) that are not inline with seller's (e.g., wanting to make a profit or set their own hours) -- platforms punishing sellers for not being in line with their objectives when those objectives are actually harming the small business
Security services extra fee	Paid security services	there are safety measures and privacy services platforms could provide but they put a premium on them and don't let all sellers use them

